

H₁₆₀

870μm

H₁₆₀

870μm

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Rotating starburst cores in the most massive galaxies at $z=2$

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credit: ESO/NAOJ/NRAO

Major changes in galaxy properties

This talk focuses on formation of the most massive galaxies

We would like to understand

- how galaxies change the star formation \longrightarrow **quenching**
- how galaxies change the morphology \longrightarrow **bulge formation**
- how galaxies change the kinematics \longrightarrow **origin of slow rotators**

star-formation

(Renzini+15)

main-sequence

red-sequence

morphology

(Wuyts+11)

disk-dominated

bulge-dominated

kinematics

(Cappellari+16)

rotation-dominated

dispersion-dominated

Where do stars form in high-redshift galaxies?

an example of massive star-forming galaxies at $z=2.5$ (Tadaki+17a)

HST (WFC3)

HST (ACS)

stellar mass

unobscured star formation

extended disk

clumpy

Where do stars form in high-redshift galaxies?

an example of massive star-forming galaxies at $z=2.5$ (Tadaki+17a)

HST (WFC3)

HST (ACS)

ALMA (870 μm)

stellar mass

unobscured star formation

obscured star formation

extended disk

clumpy

centrally-concentrated

HST-resolution 870 μm survey with ALMA

Subaru

ALMA

Subaru narrow-band survey (Tadaki+13)

ALMA observations of 25 H α -selected galaxies at $z=2.19, 2.53$ (Tadaki+17a)

Galaxy properties

Properties of H α -selected galaxies

Tadaki+17a

- we focus on ***the most massive star-forming galaxies*** with $\log M_{\text{star}} > 11$
- they are likely to quench star formation soon after the time we observe
 - our ALMA sample is almost mass-completed
 - they are located on the main-sequence of star formation
 - UV light traces $\sim 1\%$ of total star formation

Size measurements of 870 μm emission

Tadaki+17a

two examples of our ALMA targets

dust continuum emission is compact

dust continuum emission is extended

Bulge-forming galaxies with an extended disk

stellar mass-size plot

small dots:
3D-HST sample of SFGs at $z \sim 2$
(Momcheva+15)

- star-forming regions are extremely compact ($R_{1/2} < 1.5 \text{ kpc}$)
- they have an extended, exponential disk ($R_{1/2} \sim 3 \text{ kpc}$, $n \sim 1$)
- **bulge-forming galaxies**

Outside-in growth

mass-weighted age gradients (Goddard+17)

- star-forming regions are extremely compact ($R_{1/2} < 1.5 \text{ kpc}$)
- they have an extended, exponential disk ($R_{1/2} \sim 3 \text{ kpc}$, $n \sim 1$)
- **bulge-forming galaxies**

0.6''-resolution CO 3-2 observations

spatial distribution of H α emitters at $z=2.53$
(Tadaki+13)

SXDF-ALMA 2 arcmin² deep field
(Tadaki+15, Kohno+16)

CO observations of bulge-forming galaxies

- they are both associated with compact dust emission
- CO data indicates rotation of molecular gas

Starburst cores are rotation-dominated

$$v/\sigma=7$$
$$v\sim 400 \text{ km/s}$$

$$v/\sigma=4$$
$$v\sim 400 \text{ km/s}$$

**the starburst cores are rapidly rotating at $z=2.5$
do they evolve into fast rotators?**

Mergers lead to slow rotators

Illustris simulation (Penoyre+17)
major merger

see also Naab+14, Wuyts+10

Physical conditions in starburst cores

ID	$\log M_{\text{dyn}}$ (M_{\odot})	$\log M_{*}^{\text{b}}$ (M_{\odot})	$\log M_{\text{gas,CO}}^{\text{b}}$ (M_{\odot}) [$\alpha_{\text{CO}} = 4.36$]	$\log M_{\text{gas,CO}}^{\text{b}}$ (M_{\odot}) [$\alpha_{\text{CO}} = 0.8$]	$\log M_{\text{gas,3mm}}^{\text{c}}$ (M_{\odot}) [$\delta_{\text{gdr}} = 120$]
U4-16795	$11.10^{+0.13}_{-0.12}$	11.17 ± 0.15	11.01 ± 0.04	10.28 ± 0.04	10.38–10.96
U4-16504	$11.19^{+0.17}_{-0.15}$	11.10 ± 0.15	11.01 ± 0.03	10.27 ± 0.03	10.41–10.98

$\alpha=4.36$ (Galactic conversion factor)

- (1) $M_{\text{dyn}} < M_{\text{star}} + M_{\text{gas,CO}}$
- (2) $M_{\text{gas,CO}} > M_{\text{gas,3mm}}$

$\alpha=0.8$ (starburst conversion factor)

- (1) $M_{\text{dyn}} \sim M_{\text{star}} + M_{\text{gas,CO}}$
- (2) $M_{\text{gas,CO}} \sim M_{\text{gas,3mm}}$

the dense cores are likely to be formed in **extreme environments** similar to the central regions of local ULIRGs

Rest-frame 850 um emission

dust mass estimate (Dunne+00)

$$M_d = \frac{S_{850} D^2}{\kappa_d(\nu) B(\nu, T_d)}$$

$$\kappa \propto \nu^\beta$$

extrapolate rest-850um flux from observed-870 um flux assuming T_d and β
this overestimates dust mass by a factor of two

Summary

star-forming galaxies

disk-dominated

wet mergers
(Wuyts+10)

slow rotators

bulge-dominated

radial gas transport

mergers

bulge-forming galaxies
(transition phase)

disk-dominated (n=1)

bulge-dominated (n=4)

quenching

fast rotators

bulge-dominated